

Exploring the financial viability of SMR nuclear power plant in Africa: a case study in Cameroon

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Executive Summary

In addition to renewable energies, one of the most promising decarbonized energy solutions in Africa for the coming decades is the SMR plant. More than 80 SMRs are currently under construction worldwide, and the market is expected to grow by 30% by 2043. At a time when several African countries are expressing their interest in nuclear power to the IAEA, this study analyses the financial viability of SMR power plants in the African context. To this end, a futuristic case study of 6 modules of 77 MW each is considered in Cameroon. Inspired by current SMR projects, the CAPEX and OPEX models are based on referenced models from ongoing SMR projects. The financial and fiscal parameters are adapted to the local context. The results show that SMR projects are profitable in Africa, but only for a minimum capacity of 277MWe and a kWh cost of 60c€. Although the investment is still high compared with the financial capacity of African countries, an approach with a debt-to-equity ratio of 70% has been adopted. The return on investment is around 12 years and the potential dividends remain quite substantial for shareholders. A more beneficial involvement in the nuclear power sector would enable African countries to seize this market, while strengthening nuclear research and training.

1. Introduction

In Africa, financial, political and infrastructural challenges hinder the adoption of large-scale nuclear power plants. To date, only South Africa has a nuclear power plant of around 900 MW and a 1200 MW plant is currently under construction in Egypt (Felix Orikpete et al., 2023). Concerns about risks, costs and safety and security considerations have made governments hesitant about large-scale nuclear power. As a result, innovative technologies such as Small modular reactors (SMR) are disrupting conventional notions surrounding nuclear power. Smaller, more compact, and producing minimal emissions, this innovative alternative to traditional nuclear power is receiving more public and private sector attention as governments across the world scramble to meet global energy needs reliably and responsibly. Small modular reactors (SMR) are advanced nuclear reactors that have an installed capacity of up to 300 MWe/reactor (Deo, 2020). The global market for SMRs is expected to reach \$72.4 billion by 2033 and \$295 billion by 2043, representing a CAGR of 30% in this period (DTechEx, 2023). Many African countries expressed an interest on installing nuclear power systems in their respective country. by now, there is no SMR plant

installed in Africa. With many SMR projects under development around the world, including 80 by 2022 (statistica, 2022), we are entitled to wonder whether Africa will be able to accommodate this technological innovation. This study aims to assess the financial profitability of small nuclear power plant systems in African context. A futuristic case study of the installation of a small SMR power station in the locality of Biakoa in Cameroon is considered. The idea is to apply an Africa FINPLAN Case study to appreciate how such systems could financially look like.

Figure 1: SMR projects worldwide¹

2. Methodology

2.1. Site/case study

This study is based on the possibility of installing a 462 MWe small nuclear power plant in the Biakoa village (4° 19' N, 11° 17' E) in the future. This site is chosen because of its proximity to rivers for cooling purposes and to national interconnected grid for feeding generation into the grid. Biakoa is a village in Cameroon's Centre region, in the Mbam-et-Kim department. It is part of the Mbangassina commune. The idea is to connect the power station to Cameroon's Southern Interconnected System (SIN).

¹ <https://world-nuclear.org/information-library/nuclear-fuel-cycle/nuclear-power-reactors/small-nuclear-power-reactors>

Figure 2: Biakoa location (4° 19' N, 11° 17' E)

2.2. Method

The model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion Plans (FINPLAN) is a world-wide recognized financial modeling tool, which is used for financial analysis of electricity generation projects. Inputs for the FINPLAN modeling tool were divided into four headings; cost related data, technical data, economic and fiscal parameters, and financial data. Cost-related data included investments, O&M costs, fuel costs, and decommissioning costs. Technical data involved plant's power generation capacity, construction period, commercial operational year, plant life time, and Plant Capacity Factor. Economic parameters referred to revenues, expenditures, inflation, exchange rates, taxes, etc. Financial parameters included credits, loans, bonds, and equity, etc (Ilife,2008; Vanhoutteghem, 1986, Nuryanti, 2016; Ishan bin Haji Bakar, 1989). Figure 3 shows how the FINPLAN modeling tool converts from input into output parameters for each year.

Figure 3: FINPLAN inputs and outputs

The model provides outputs as cash flows, balance sheet, financial ratios, NPV, IRR, etc. Foreign currency, exchange rate, and inflation rate were considered as the important parameters in financial analysis. As such, the FINPLAN modeling tool allows options for considering one or multiple foreign currencies in the financial analysis. In the data on a product sale/purchase, the FINPLAN modeling tool needed the number of units of electrical energy to be sold per annum and the unit electricity selling price data over the plant's economic lifetime.

2.3. Data

Given that very few SMRs have been installed anywhere in the world, the data considered for this case study is based on the experience of installations that have already been completed or are in the process of being completed. As specified in the previous paragraph, the data are presented in four (4) parts: cost related data, technical data, economic and fiscal parameters, and financial data.

2.3.1. Cost related data

This includes investments, O&M costs, fuel costs, and decommissioning costs. Current SMR plants capital and operational expenses have a wide range of uncertainty (Sabharwall, 2015; Vogel, 2017).

- Capital: The EIA has estimated an overnight capital cost for a new nuclear LR to be \$5,460/kW, adjusted to 2015 USD (Iliffe,2008), i.e. €5,027.96/kW. This value is considered in this study due to the low maturity of SMR technology.
- O&M Costs: Boldon and Sabharwall (2014) have surveyed operation and maintenance (O&M) estimates in literature, determining an appropriate operational estimate of \$18.00 per MWh of power plant capacity, that means O&M equals € 16.5757/MWh using 2015 USD. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission Fees, nuclear waste management costs are included in that O&M cost),
- Fuel and re-fueling costs have been estimated at \$9.10 per MWh of power plant capacity. That means fuel cost equals € 8.37994 /MWh using 2015 USD
- The Decommissioning cost is estimated at around 5 billion euros per year for this project.

2.3.2. Technical data

Cameroon's SMR project (CSMRP) is aiming for 462 MW installed capacity, with an installed capacity of 77 MW per module. As done in Romania, the Cameroon's SMR project is estimated to create nearly 200 permanent jobs, 1500 construction jobs and 2300 manufacturing and component assembly jobs, as well as facility operation and maintenance jobs over the 60-year life of the facility (Kuznetsov& Barkatullah,2009). Assuming that Cameroon will take the same steps as the referenced one, Romania, we have the following data:

Table 1: Cameroon-Biakoa SMR technical data

Technical data	
Plant size:	462 MW
Number of SMR modules	6 (77MW each)
Plant Capacity Factor	90%
Plant life time	60 years
First year operation	2035
Construction duration	5 years
Decommissioning:	5 years

2.3.3. Economic and fiscal parameters

- Exchange Rates: Local currency in Cameroon is CFA Franc codified under XAF. Since 1 January 1999, the parity of the CFA franc has been 655.957 CFA francs to the euro. The operation of the franc zone is based on the principle of a fixed parity between the CFA franc and the euro (France).
- Inflation Rate: The rate at which the prices of goods and services in an economy are increasing over time. It has been taken equals to 5% in this study.
- Interest Rate: Assume to be 8%. Due to the novelty of this SMR technology&Market, the interest rate may be very far from reality. This calls for a sensitivity analysis of this parameter.
- Tax Parameters: Income Tax and VAT on investment are assumed equals to 19.25% in Cameroon context.
- We assume in this study that the electricity produced must not be sold above the value currently applied, i.e. 60XAF/KWh

2.3.4. Financial Data

Financial parameters included credits, loans, bonds, and equity, etc. In this study, all investment values have been estimated as presented in paragraph 2.3.1 and the distribution between loans and equity have been adjusted to have a Debt-to-Equity ratio of 70%.

2.4. Scenarios/sensitivities analysis

Three different postulated scenarios were created for the calculation of financial and economic analysis of the Biakoa nuclear Power project in Cameroon.

They are the variation of electricity price, the variation of the size of the power plant (investment cost) and the variation of the interest rate. Based on the fixed cost financial contract, plant data, general data, and some assumptions on O&M costs, fuel costs, decommissioning costs, and PCFs, etc. Net Present Value, Internal rate of return and Payback period were calculated for each scenario.

Table 2: three scenarios applied in Cameroon nuclear project

Scenario	Assumptions/variations	Rationale
1- Electricity price	Base value: 8c€/kWh [5-9, 1]c€/kwh,	The price of electricity can vary according to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • changes in the price of uranium fuel, which may be affected by market growth; • variations in waste management costs, which have become more restrictive; • And more generally, O&M costs variations.
2- Quantity of Electricity produced	Base value: 90% of nominal (3642.4GWh) [50%-90%, 10%]	The amount of energy produced can be influenced by two main factors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the installed power plant has 6 modules, which can be shut down from time to time for rotating maintenance; • there may be delays or interruptions in the supply of fuel.
3- Interest rate	Base value: 8% [2%- 8%, 1%],	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The interest rate applied to loans can affect the profitability of the project.

3. Results

3.1. Scenario 1: electricity price variation

The base value of the price of electricity is 0.8c€/kWh, corresponding to the average value applied in Cameroon. This first scenario analyses the impact of the variation in the price of electricity on the profitability of the system, by varying the price of electricity from 5c€/kWh to 9c€/kWh. The five levels of electricity prices are applied with the aim of evaluating its impact on NPV and IRR.

Figure 4 shows that at electricity prices below €6c/kWh, the NPV remains positive, but the IRR is more restrictive, at less than 8%, than at electricity prices above €7c/kWh. This reinforces the need to assess the impact of interest rates

Figure 4: influence of electricity price on NPV and IRR

Figure 3 shows that a shareholder will only be able to receive a dividend after 10 years of operation, corresponding to the borrowing period for electricity sold at 9c€/kWh. However, for lower electricity prices, the waiting time to receive the first dividend will be even longer, on average 3 years for each lower unit increment in the electricity price.

Figure 5: influence of electricity prices on dividends

3.2. Scenario 2: variation of energy produced

Scenario 2 looks at the impact of any variation in the amount of energy supplied by the plant on the profitability of the system. By varying the power factor from 90% to 50%, as shown in Figure 6, we observe a drop in NPV and IRR. For a PCF of less than 53%, the NPV becomes negative, and for a PCF of less than 75%, the IRR becomes less than 8%.

Figure 6: Influence of Power Capacity on NPV and IRR

Figure 7: Influence of energy produced on NPV and IRR

Figure 7 shows that when the FCP is at 90%, it takes around 12 years to reach the first dividend. I would add an average of 3 years each time there is a 10% reduction in production capacity and the NPV remains positive.

3.3. Scenario 3: variation of interest rate

This last scenario measures the behavior of NPV and IRR when the interest rate changes. By varying the interest rate from 2% to the baseline of 8%, it is assumed that the system remains profitable with a positive NPV and an IRR above 8%.

Figure 8: Influence of interest rate on NPV and IRR

On the other hand, if we look at figure xx, which shows the influence of the interest rate on dividends, we can see that dividends are higher and are received after only 5 years of operation.

Figure 9: influence of the interest rate on dividends

4. Discussion

As with renewable energy systems, the development of small-scale nuclear power plants should be considered in the African electricity market. Results obtained from a case study of the installation of an SMR power plant in Cameroon, as presented in the previous paragraph, point to a profitable business. Figure 3 shows the variation in the price of electricity allows a certain amount of flexibility in terms of profitability, but remains restrictive in order to achieve an IRR of over 8% and a positive NPV. In fact, it can be noticed that the

SMR power plant in this study can only be profitable if the price of electricity is over 6c€/kWh. This would be the cheapest tariff currently applied in Cameroon, and in many others countries in Africa. Similarly, when the power factor is less than 53%, the IRR is less than 8% and the NPV is less than 10% (fig 5). So, the idea that SMRs represent a great opportunity for nuclear power in Africa could be verified, but it is important to know that, there is a minimum size that is financially acceptable, at a particular electricity price. the installation of a nuclear power station only seems profitable if it has a minimum output around 277 MWe for the Cameroon case considered. Loans, which make up just over 70% of the capital, at an interest rate of 8%, have very little impact on the profitability of the system. The dividends therefore remain virtually constant throughout the lifetime of the plant, but the loan repayment time increases as the interest rate rises. the reduction in the interest rate keeps the system profitable at a slightly stable IRR. the price of electricity, the energy produced and the interest rate should be analysed together to extract the optimum scenario applicable. One perspective on this work would be to compare this solution with renewable energy solutions of the same order of scale.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the opportunity that SMR plants represent for the African electricity market. The case study selected in Cameroon shows that an SMR plant can be profitable there for capacities of over 277MWe for electricity sold at a price of 8c€/kWh, i.e. around 53 XAF/kWh in local currency. However, increasing electricity production (number of SMR modules or installed power) would consequently increase profit and electricity supply. A fluctuation in the market price allows a minimum electricity sale price of 6c€/kWh (36 XAF/kWh), i.e. almost half the rate currently applied in the country.

This study also shows that, despite the fact that SMRs are designed to reduce the capital costs of nuclear installations compared with known large power plants, it is nevertheless true that the investment cost of a small nuclear power plant remains high compared with the financial capacities of African countries. African governments would do well to anticipate this new nuclear market, so as to be able to reduce the financial and technical impact when investment decisions have to be made, in particular by strengthening research and training in the sector. In the same vein, the objective of increasing scientific advice in the decarbonized energy sector, with nuclear power included should be densified in Africa.

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